

Appendix A. Keywords/ Queries.

The queries are given below for each database searched: Scopus, PubMed, and IEEE Xplore..

Query #	Query Line
1 (Scopus)	(TITLE-ABS-KEY("stress"))
	AND
	(TITLE-ABS-KEY("heart rate variability" OR HRV))
2 (PubMed)	AND
	(TITLE-ABS-KEY("wearable device" OR "wearable technology" OR "smartwatch" OR "wrist-worn device" OR "fitness tracker"))
	(("stress"[Title/Abstract])
3 (IEEE Explorer)	AND
	(("heart rate variability"[Title/Abstract] OR HRV[Title/Abstract])
	AND
	(("wearable device"[Title/Abstract] OR "wearable technology"[Title/Abstract] OR smartwatch[Title/Abstract] OR "wrist-worn device"[Title/Abstract] OR "fitness tracker"[Title/Abstract])

Appendix B. Basic Extracted Data

#	Article Title	Country(s)	Study Settings	Sample Size	Gender distribution ¹	Mean Age	Placement	Wrist Sensor	Stress Labeling Method	Stressor Type
1	Alignment Between Heart Rate Variability From Fitness Trackers and Perceived Stress: Perspectives From a Large-Scale In Situ Longitudinal Study of Information Workers [1]	USA, Finland	Real-World	327	66%	35	Wrist	Garmin Vivosmart 3	Self-reported	Naturalistic Daily Life
2	A multi-component intervention to affect physical activity, sleep length and stress levels in office workers [2]	Denmark	Real-World	63	44%	42	Wrist	Garmin Vivosmart 3	Proprietary automated estimation	Naturalistic Daily Life
3	Analysis of the driver's stress level while driving in Truck Platooning [3]	Italy	Real-World	0	N/A	N/A	Wrist	Other	Protocol-defined (tasks/phases)	Contextual Real-World Events
4	Analysis of the Relationship between Personality Traits and Driving Stress Using a Non-Intrusive Wearable Device [4]	Germany, Spain	Real-World	0	N/A	N/A	Chest	No	Contextual/observational inference	Contextual Real-World Events
5	A New Intelligent Approach for Automatic Stress Level Assessment Based on Multiple Physiological Parameters Monitoring [5]	Portugal, Spain	Lab-based	15	N/A	N/A	Chest, Wrist, Finger	Other	Protocol-defined (tasks/phases)	Protocol based Cognitive Stressors
6	Application level performance evaluation of wearable devices for stress classification with explainable AI [6]	Turkey, Germany, United Kingdom	Lab-based	22	50%	28	Wrist, Finger	Garmin Vivosmart 3	Contextual/observational inference	Protocol based Cognitive Stressors
7	A Sensitivity Analysis of Biophysiological Responses of Stress for Wearable Sensors in Connected Health [7]	Ireland, UK	Lab-based	10	60%	N/A	Chest, Finger, Arm	Other	Protocol-defined (tasks/phases)	Protocol based Cognitive Stressors
8	Assessment of Stress and Well-Being of Japanese Employees Using Wearable Devices for Sleep Monitoring Combined With Ecological Momentary Assessment: Pilot Observational Study [8]	Japan	Real-World	20	50%	42	Wrist	Other	Self-reported	Naturalistic Daily Life
9	Associations between Sleep Quality and Heart Rate Variability; Implications for a Biological Model of Stress Detection Using Wearable Technology [9]	Australia	Real-World	42	100%	N/A	Chest	No	Contextual/observational inference	N/A

¹ % of males in population of the study

10	Automatic and Intelligent Stressor Identification Based on Photoplethysmography Analysis [10]	Qatar	Real-World	20	N/A	N/A	Finger	No	Protocol-defined (tasks/phases)	Protocol based Emotional or Visual Stimuli
11	Comparison of automatic and physiologically-based feature selection methods for classifying physiological stress using heart rate and pulse rate variability indices [11]	Italy, Serbia, Slovakia	Real-World	30	66%	27	Wrist	Empatica E4	Protocol-defined (tasks/phases)	Protocol based Cognitive Stressors
12	Discovery of associative patterns between workplace sound level and physiological well-being using wearable devices and empirical Bayes modeling [12]	USA	Real-World	231	50%	44	Chest, Neck	No	Contextual/observational inference	Naturalistic Daily Life
13	Effects of Missing Data on Heart Rate Variability Metrics [13]	Spain	Lab-based	20	100%	28	Chest, Wrist	Apple Watch	Protocol-defined (tasks/phases)	Protocol-based breathing
14	Enhancing Well-Being and Alleviating Stress via Wearable-Driven Emotion Recognition and EQ Intentional Practice With Deep Reinforcement Learning [14]	USA	Real-World	50	N/A	N/A	Wrist	Empatica E4	Self-reported	Naturalistic Daily Life
15	Exploring Undergraduate Students' Psychological Stress in the Mathematics Classroom with Fitness Trackers [15]	USA	Lab-based	29	38%	N/A	Wrist	Other	Contextual/observational inference	Cognitive Stressors
16	Factors Associated With Longitudinal Psychological and Physiological Stress in Health Care Workers During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Observational Study Using Apple Watch Data [16]	USA	Real-World	361	31%	36,8	Wrist	Garmin Forerunner	Self-reported	Naturalistic Daily Life
17	Heart Rate Variability-Based Mental Stress Detection: An Explainable Machine Learning Approach [17]	India, United Kingdom	Dataset	15	N/a	N/A	Wrist	Apple Watch	Protocol-defined (tasks/phases)	Contextual Real-World Events
18	HRV and Stress: A Mixed-Methods Approach for Comparison of Wearable Heart Rate Sensors for Biofeedback [18]	United Kingdom, Turkey	Lab-based	32	N/a	N/A	Chest	No	Contextual/observational inference	Protocol based Cognitive Stressors
19	HRV Features as Viable Physiological Markers for Stress Detection Using Wearable Devices [19]	United Kingdom	Real-World	4	N/a	N/A	Wrist, Arm, Chest	Empatica E4	Contextual/observational inference	Contextual Real-World Events
20	HRV in Active-Duty Special Forces and Public Order Military Personnel [20]	Italy	Real-World	33	100%	36	Chest, Wrist	Apple Watch	No explicit labeling / continuous	Naturalistic Daily Life
21	Integrated mental stress smartwatch based on sweat cortisol and HRV sensors [21]	China	Real-World	5	n/a	N/A	Chest	No	Contextual/observational inference	Contextual Real-World Events
22	Investigating How Auditory and Visual Stimuli Promote Recovery After Stress With Potential Applications for Workplace Stress and Burnout: Protocol for a Randomized Trial [22]	USA	Lab-based	80	n/a	N/A	Wrist	Other	Contextual/observational inference	Protocol based Cognitive Stressors

23	Mental fatigue detection using a wearable commodity device and machine learning [23]	Greece	Lab-based	30	81%	24,6	Chest, Wrist, Arm	Apple Watch, Empatica E4, Polar	Contextual/observational inference	Protocol based Cognitive Stressors
24	Mental Stress Assessment Using Ultra Short Term HRV Analysis Based on Non-Linear Method [24]	South Korea	Lab-based	74	96%	N/A	Chest	No	Contextual/observational inference	Protocol based Cognitive Stressors
25	Multi-domain analysis of ultra-short-term HRV for breathing pattern classification in wearable health devices [25]	India	Lab-based	60	100%	N/A	Chest	No	Contextual/observational inference	Protocol based Cognitive Stressors
26	Nurse evaluation of stress levels during CPR training with heart rate variability using smartwatches according to their personality: A prospective, observational study [26]	South Korea	Lab-based	132	8%	27	Wrist	Other	No explicit labeling / continuous	Contextual Real-World Events
27	Optimization of Wearable Biosensor Data for Stress Classification Using Machine Learning and Explainable AI [27]	India	Lab-based	30	89%	N/A	Wrist	Apple Watch	Contextual/observational inference	Protocol based Cognitive Stressors
28	Personal Stress-Level Clustering and Decision-Level Smoothing to Enhance the Performance of Ambulatory Stress Detection With Smartwatches [28]	Turkey, Italy	Real-World	32	69%	N/A	Wrist	Empatica E4	Self-reported	Protocol based Cognitive Stressors
29	Preprocessing Methods for Ambulatory HRV Analysis Based on HRV Distribution, Variability and Characteristics (DVC) [29]	France	Lab-based	67	n/a	N/A	Wrist	Empatica E4 + Other	Protocol-defined (tasks/phases)	Protocol based Cognitive Stressors
30	Real-Life Stress Level Monitoring Using Smart Bands in the Light of Contextual Information [30]	Turkey, Italy, United Kingdom	Real-World	15	60%	28	Chest, Wrist, Finger	Other	Self-reported	Protocol based Cognitive Stressors
31	Real Time Worker Stress Prediction in a Smart Factory Assembly Line [31]	Saudi Arabia, France, Pakistan, USA	Dataset	35	n/a	N/A	Wrist	Empatica E4	Contextual/observational inference	Protocol based Cognitive Stressors
32	Relieving the burden of intensive labeling for stress monitoring in the wild by using semi-supervised learning [32]	Germany, Turkey	Real-World	15	60%	28,5	Wrist	Empatica E4	Protocol-defined (tasks/phases)	Naturalistic Daily Life
33	Stress Detection Through Wrist-Based Electrodermal Activity Monitoring and Machine Learning [33]	Canada	Lab-based	15	n/a	N/A	Wrist	Empatica E4	Protocol-defined (tasks/phases)	Protocol based Cognitive Stressors
34	Stress Detection With Single PPG Sensor by Orchestrating Multiple Denoising and Peak-Detecting Methods [34]	South Korea	Lab-based	15	n/a	N/A	Wrist	Empatica E4	Protocol-defined (tasks/phases)	Protocol based Cognitive Stressors
35	The Feasibility of Wearable and Self-Report Stress Detection Measures in a Semi-Controlled Lab Environment [35]	USA	Lab-based	22	n/a	28,3	Wrist	Empatica E4	Protocol-defined (tasks/phases)	Protocol based Cognitive Stressors

36	The impact of ambient noise on patron stress levels while studying in the library [36]	USA	Real-World	32	29%	23,26	Wrist	Empatica E4	Contextual/observational inference	Contextual Real-World Events
37	Understanding Drivers' Stress and Interactions With Vehicle Systems Through Naturalistic Data Analysis [37]	Germany, USA	Real-World	82	n/a	N/A	Wrist	Garmin Vivosmart 3	Contextual/observational inference	Contextual Real-World Events
38	Using apple watch ECG data for heart rate variability monitoring and stress prediction: A pilot study [38]	Canada	Real-World	36	56%	36,4	Wrist	Other	Self-reported	Naturalistic Daily Life
39	Wearable derived cardiovascular responses to stressors in free-living conditions [39]	USA	Real-World	115	56%	35,4	Wrist	Apple Watch	Protocol-defined (tasks/phases)	Naturalistic Daily Life
40	Wearable Technology: A Wellbeing Option for Serving Police Officers and Staff? A Comparison of Results of a Pilot Study with Firearms Officers and a Group of Mixed Officers and Staff [40]	United Kingdom	Real-World	41	n/a	N/A	Wrist	Other	Self-reported	Naturalistic Daily Life
41	Work-related stress, psychophysiological strain, and recovery among on-site construction personnel [41]	China, Nigeria	Real-World	21	100%	41,76	Wrist	Garmin Vivosmart 3	No explicit labeling / continuous	Naturalistic Daily Life

Appendix C. JBI Critical Appraisal

#	Article Title	JBI Checklist type	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	Score	Of
1	Alignment Between Heart Rate Variability From Fitness Trackers and Perceived Stress: Perspectives From a Large-Scale In Situ Longitudinal Study of Information Workers [1]	JBI Analytical Cross Sectional Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes				9	9
2	A multi-component intervention to affect physical activity, sleep length and stress levels in office workers [2]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes				8	9
3	Analysis of the driver's stress level while driving in Truck Platooning [3]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Unclear				7	9
4	Analysis of the Relationship between Personality Traits and Driving Stress Using a Non-Intrusive Wearable Device [4]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes				8	9
5	A New Intelligent Approach for Automatic Stress Level Assessment Based on Multiple Physiological Parameters Monitoring [5]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes				8	9
6	Application level performance evaluation of wearable devices for stress classification with explainable AI [6]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes				8	9
7	A Sensitivity Analysis of Biophysiological Responses of Stress for Wearable Sensors in Connected Health [7]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes				8	9
8	Assessment of Stress and Well-Being of Japanese Employees Using Wearable Devices for Sleep Monitoring Combined With Ecological Momentary Assessment: Pilot Observational Study [8]	JBI Analytical Cross-Sectional Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes					7.5	8
9	Associations between Sleep Quality and Heart Rate Variability; Implications for a Biological Model of Stress Detection Using Wearable Technology [9]	JBI Analytical Cross-Sectional Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes					8	8
10	Automatic and Intelligent Stressor Identification Based on Photoplethysmography Analysis [10]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes				8	9
11	Comparison of automatic and physiologically-based feature selection methods for classifying physiological stress using heart rate and pulse rate variability indices [11]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes				8	9
12	Discovery of associative patterns between workplace sound level and physiological wellbeing using	JBI Analytical Cross-Sectional Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes					9	9

	wearable devices and empirical Bayes modeling [12]															
13	Effects of Missing Data on Heart Rate Variability Metrics [13]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes				8	9
14	Enhancing Well-Being and Alleviating Stress via Wearable-Driven Emotion Recognition and EQ Intentional Practice With Deep Reinforcement Learning [14]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes				8	9
15	Exploring Undergraduate Students' Psychological Stress in the Mathematics Classroom with Fitness Trackers [15]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes				8	9
16	Factors Associated With Longitudinal Psychological and Physiological Stress in Health Care Workers During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Observational Study Using Apple Watch Data [16]	JBI Analytical Cohort Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		11	11
17	Heart Rate Variability-Based Mental Stress Detection: An Explainable Machine Learning Approach [17]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes				8	9
18	HRV and Stress: A Mixed-Methods Approach for Comparison of Wearable Heart Rate Sensors for Biofeedback [18]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes				8	9
19	HRV Features as Viable Physiological Markers for Stress Detection Using Wearable Devices [19]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes				8	9
20	HRV in Active-Duty Special Forces and Public Order Military Personnel [20]	JBI Analytical Cross-Sectional Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes					8	8
21	Integrated mental stress smartwatch based on sweat cortisol and HRV sensors [21]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear				7.5	9
22	Investigating How Auditory and Visual Stimuli Promote Recovery After Stress With Potential Applications for Workplace Stress and Burnout: Protocol for a Randomized Trial [22]	JBI Checklist for Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs)	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	9	12
23	Mental fatigue detection using a wearable commodity device and machine learning [23]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes				8	9
24	Mental Stress Assessment Using Ultra Short Term HRV Analysis Based on Non-Linear Method [24]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes				8	9
25	Multi-domain analysis of ultra-short-term HRV for breathing pattern classification in wearable health devices [25]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes				8	9
26	Nurse evaluation of stress levels during CPR training with heart rate variability using smartwatches according to their personality: A prospective, observational study [26]	JBI Analytical Cross-Sectional Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes				8	8

27	Optimization of Wearable Biosensor Data for Stress Classification Using Machine Learning and Explainable AI [27]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes					8	9
28	Personal Stress-Level Clustering and Decision-Level Smoothing to Enhance the Performance of Ambulatory Stress Detection With Smartwatches [28]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes					8	9
29	Preprocessing Methods for Ambulatory HRV Analysis Based on HRV Distribution, Variability and Characteristics (DVC) [29]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes					8	9
30	Real-Life Stress Level Monitoring Using Smart Bands in the Light of Contextual Information [30]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes					8	9
31	Real Time Worker Stress Prediction in a Smart Factory Assembly Line [31]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes					8	9
32	Relieving the burden of intensive labeling for stress monitoring in the wild by using semi-supervised learning [32]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes					8	9
33	Stress Detection Through Wrist-Based Electrodermal Activity Monitoring and Machine Learning [33]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes					8	9
34	Stress Detection With Single PPG Sensor by Orchestrating Multiple Denoising and Peak-Detecting Methods [34]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes					8	9
35	The Feasibility of Wearable and Self-Report Stress Detection Measures in a Semi-Controlled Lab Environment [35]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes					8	9
36	The impact of ambient noise on patron stress levels while studying in the library [36]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear					7.5	9
37	Understanding Drivers' Stress and Interactions With Vehicle Systems Through Naturalistic Data Analysis [37]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes					8	9
38	Using apple watch ECG data for heart rate variability monitoring and stress prediction: A pilot study [38]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes					8	9
39	Wearable derived cardiovascular responses to stressors in free-living conditions [39]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes					8	9
40	Wearable Technology: A Wellbeing Option for Serving Police Officers and Staff? A Comparison of Results of a Pilot Study with Firearms Officers and a Group of Mixed Officers and Staff [40]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes					8	9
41	Work-related stress, psychophysiological strain, and recovery among on-site construction personnel [41]	JBI Quasi-Experimental Studies Checklist	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes					8	9

Appendix D. PRISMA Checklist

#	Item	PRISMA 2020 Criteria	Status
TITLE			
1	Title	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Yes
ABSTRACT			
2	Abstract	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist.	Yes
INTRODUCTION			
3	Rationale	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	Yes
4	Objectives	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	Yes
METHODS			
5	Eligibility criteria	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	Yes
6	Information sources	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	Yes
7	Search strategy	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	Yes
8	Selection process	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Yes
9	Data collection process	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Yes
10	Data items	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought, and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.	Yes
11	Study risk of bias assessment	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Yes
12	Effect measures	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	N/A

#	Item	PRISMA 2020 Criteria	Status
13	Synthesis methods	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis, how data were prepared for presentation or synthesis, any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses, and any other methods used.	Yes
14	Reporting bias assessment	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	Yes
15	Certainty assessment	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	Yes
RESULTS			
16	Study selection	Describe the results of the search and selection process, including findings of searches of other sources, and report the number of studies included in the review, preferably using a flow diagram.	Yes
17	Study characteristics	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	Yes
18	Risk of bias in studies	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	Yes
19	Results of individual studies	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	Yes
20	Results of syntheses	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies, present results of all statistical syntheses conducted, and indicate the certainty of the evidence.	Yes
21	Reporting biases	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	Yes
22	Certainty of evidence	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	Yes
DISCUSSION			
23	Discussion	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence; discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review; discuss any limitations of the review processes used; and describe implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	Yes
OTHER INFORMATION			
24	Registration and protocol	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state that the review was not registered. Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	N/A
25	Support	Describe sources of financial or other support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	Yes
26	Competing interests	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	Yes

#	Item	PRISMA 2020 Criteria	Status
27	Availability of data, code and other materials	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	Yes

Legend: Yes = reported; N/A = not applicable (narrative synthesis, no meta-analysis performed).

Appendix E. Bibliography of research papers

- [1] G. J. Martinez *et al.*, "Alignment between Heart Rate Variability from Fitness Trackers and Perceived Stress: Perspectives from a Large-Scale in Situ Longitudinal Study of Information Workers," *JMIR Hum. Factors*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 1–21, 2022, doi: 10.2196/33754.
- [2] L. H. Larsen, M. H. Lauritzen, M. Sinkjaer, and T. W. Kjaer, "A multi-component intervention to affect physical activity, sleep length and stress levels in office workers," *Smart Health*, vol. 22, no. September, p. 100219, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.smhl.2021.100219.
- [3] P. Gandini, L. Studer, M. Zecchini, and M. Ponti, "Analysis of the driver's stress level while driving in Truck Platooning," *Multimodal Transportation*, vol. 4, no. 1, p. 100185, 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.multra.2024.100185.
- [4] W. D. Scherz, V. Corcoba, D. Melendi, R. Seepold, N. Martínez Madrid, and J. A. Ortega, "Analysis of the Relationship between Personality Traits and Driving Stress Using a Non-Intrusive Wearable Device," *Electronics (Switzerland)*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 1–23, 2024, doi: 10.3390/electronics13010159.
- [5] G. Ribeiro, O. Postolache, and F. Ferrero, "A New Intelligent Approach for Automatic Stress Level Assessment Based on Multiple Physiological Parameters Monitoring," *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 73, pp. 1–14, 2024, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2023.3342218.
- [6] N. Chalabianloo, Y. S. Can, M. Umair, C. Sas, and C. Ersoy, "Application level performance evaluation of wearable devices for stress classification with explainable AI," *Pervasive Mob. Comput.*, vol. 87, p. 101703, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.pmcj.2022.101703.
- [7] T. Iqbal *et al.*, "A Sensitivity Analysis of Biophysiological Responses of Stress for Wearable Sensors in Connected Health," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 93567–93579, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3082423.
- [8] S. Kinoshita *et al.*, "Assessment of Stress and Well-Being of Japanese Employees Using Wearable Devices for Sleep Monitoring Combined With Ecological Momentary Assessment: Pilot Observational Study," *JMIR Form. Res.*, vol. 8, 2024, doi: 10.2196/49396.
- [9] T. Chalmers *et al.*, "Associations between Sleep Quality and Heart Rate Variability; Implications for a Biological Model of Stress Detection Using Wearable Technology," *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, vol. 19, no. 9, pp. 1–10, 2022, doi: 10.3390/ijerph19095770.
- [10] S. Elzeiny and M. Qaraqe, "Automatic and Intelligent Stressor Identification Based on Photoplethysmography Analysis," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 68498–68510, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3077358.
- [11] M. Iovino, I. Lazic, T. Loncar-Turukalo, M. Javorka, R. Pernice, and L. Faes, "Comparison of automatic and physiologically-based feature selection methods for classifying physiological stress using heart rate and pulse rate variability indices," *Physiol. Meas.*, vol. 45, no. 11, 2024, doi: 10.1088/1361-6579/ad9234.
- [12] K. Srinivasan *et al.*, "Discovery of associative patterns between workplace sound level and physiological wellbeing using wearable devices and empirical Bayes modeling," *NPJ Digit. Med.*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 1–10, 2023, doi: 10.1038/s41746-022-00727-1.
- [13] D. Cajal, D. Hernando, J. Lázaro, P. Laguna, E. Gil, and R. Bailón, "Effects of Missing Data on Heart Rate Variability Metrics," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 15, pp. 1–22, 2022, doi: 10.3390/s22155774.
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